

APPROACHES OF CRIMINAL GEOGRAPHY IN DIFFERENT SPATIAL LEVELS FOR THE ADAPTATION OPPORTUNITIES OF MODERN

Dr. Zsuzsa Piskóti Kovács

Faculty of Earth Science and Engineering,
Geography-Geo informatics Institute, University of Miskolc

Abstract

This research paper is to analyse the spatial distribution of crime in different regional scales: country, county and settlement level – it covers the analysis of the North-Hungarian Region. The overall objective is to explore the connection between crime indexes and socio-economic factors. To evaluate the criminal situation of Hungary adequately, it is necessary to analyse its statistics in international context.

Counties of Hungary are the next level of analysis. Before demonstrating county level crime maps, it is necessary to figure the long-term crime data of Hungary – this part could be interpreted as a passage from larger to lower scale. For this reason I study the progress of known offences and offenders between 1970 and 2012. Evaluating the criminal situation of Hungarian counties was necessary to introduce the most detailed research level. I study that what kind of differences could be detected between the distribution of offences and offenders and I attempt to limit crime attractive and offender exporter spatial units – emphasizing the situation of the region analyzed in detail.

This analysis focuses on exploring regional specificities and the backgrounds of regional arrangement. I examine the following issues: spatial pattern of crime, mapping crime clusters and modeling spatial relations; including the analysis of socio-economic factors and crime relation, moreover I attempt to create crime surface model. Finally I demonstrate the connection between social factors and crime in the example of four settlements of Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County.

Key Word: North-Hungarian Region, socio-economic factors, spatial pattern of crime, crime indexes.

INTRODUCTION

Criminal geography is a research field, which analyses the spatial distribution of crime and the results are demonstrated primarily by crime maps. Experts have dealt with the geography of crime since the beginning of criminological researches. There are several articles in Hungarian literature as well, which analyse the connection between crime and social factors. In Hungary there are two Ph. D. dissertations about criminal geography in the field of earth sciences, in addition I would mention the Ph.D. dissertation of ERDEI (2014) in the field of police science.

My Ph. D. dissertation focuses on an issue that was marginal in Hungarian literature: it analyses crime in GIS environment. Nevertheless significant international literature are available concerning this topic (e. g. CAMERON 2001; APPIAHENE – GYAMFI 2003; ACKERMAN et al. 2004; HARRIES 2006; WOLFF – ASCHE 2009; CECCATO – DOLMEN 2011; FERREIRA ET AL. 2012; LEI 2011; WANG ET AL. 2013).

The another novelty of the dissertation is that it applies different spatial statistical methods – based on the guidance of international literature (e. g. MESSNER – ANSELIN 2004; CAHILL – MULLIGAN 2007; CRACOLICI – UBERTI 2008; BREETZKE 2010; ANDRESEN 2011); in this regard it tends to exceed the simple thematic mapping and try to visualize the results in a quantitative way.

NEW SCIENTIFIC RESULTS

Studying long-term Hungarian crime data the following conclusion can be done:

Thesis 1. Number of known offences and offenders dramatically increased after the transition if we consider the 1970-2012 period (Figure 1 and 2). This increase can be explained adequately by different theories of crime, but one must not forget about the fact that law enforcement agencies worked under a forceful pressure by power in order to produce favourable statistics. In my opinion the dramatically increase can be interpreted as the common consequence of these two mentioned phenomena.

My aim was to describe the criminal situation of Hungary by demonstrating its crime maps. Although doubts often emerge relating to reliability of crime statistics, in my view these data can be an appropriate basis for different social geographical analysis. The passage of time can facilitate that, because even more data will be available, better corrections

of outlier data could be done, in addition it will be possible to explore certain long-term trends. Considering spatial distribution of crime the following statements can be done in county level:

Figure 1. Change of known offences between 1970 and 2012 in Hungary

(Source: ERÜBS, ENYÜBS³)

Figure 2. Change of known offenders between 1970 and 2012 in Hungary

(Source: ERÜBS, ENYÜBS)

Thesis 2. Number of known offences is the highest in Budapest according to its calculated mean (in the proportion of population) based on the period of 1990-2012. Budapest is followed by Somogy, Csongrád, Hajdú-Bihar, Fejér, Komárom- Esztergom, and Baranya Counties. The least offences were committed in Vas, Nógrád, and Békés Counties in the analysed period (Figure 3). Regarding to known offenders we can make the conclusion, that the most offenders came from Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County in the analysed period (Figure 4), value of the index is 129 % of the country mean. This county is followed by Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg, Hajdú-Bihar, and Komárom-Esztergom Counties. The least offenders are from Győr-Moson-Sopron, Vas, and Fejér Counties.

A. If we analyse the mean of known offences in case of western and eastern counties (without the data of capital town), it can be concluded that the western counties of Hungary have higher rates slightly: the value is 390,2 in case of Western-Hungarian counties is, while in case of eastern ones it is 374,87.

B. In case of known offenders the eastern counties have higher rates: mean of eastern counties is 122,69 (without Budapest), while in the case of western ones it is 109,15. Therefore a more significant difference (~11 %) can be established between the western and eastern counties.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of offences after the transition in Hungary
(Source: own edition based on crimestat.b-m.hu and KSH⁴ data)

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of offenders after the transition in

Hungary

Thesis 3. According to the numbers of known offences and offenders the Hungarian counties can be classified into three classes: crime attractive (Class 1), neutral spatial units (Class 2) and offender exporter (Class 3) (Figure 5). Offender exporter counties can be found mainly in East-Hungary, while crime attractive ones are related basically to Transdanubium.

Figure 5. Classes based on ranks of known offences and offenders (Source: own edition)

After demonstrating the spatial distribution of crime using county level data it is worth to analyse what kind of social and economic factors could stand in the background. For this purpose I selected some social and economic factors, which could connect to crime indexes. As the first step I drew the scatter plots of variables; if linear connection could be considered I calculated Pearson correlation coefficient.

Thesis 4. Concerning the connection between county level crime data and some selected social and economic variables the following statements can be made:

- Spatial inequalities of GDP per capita does not explain the spatial distribution of known offences in the relation of Hungarian counties (Figure 6).
- There is a linear connection between known offenders and activity, employment and unemployment rates. Strong negative connection can be detected in case of activity and employment rate, and strong

positive connection can be found in case of unemployment rate. According to that we can say that the selected indexes describing labour market have a significant influence on the distribution of offences in county scale.

Figure 6. Connection between number of offences and GDP (purchasing power parity)

(Source: own edition according to KSH⁵ data)

According to my assumption the spatial distribution of offences and offenders is not random, settlements having high crime rates could be found in the neighbourhood of settlements having similar high crime values, and settlements characterized by low crime values are close to settlements having similar low crime rates. To examine this assumption I calculated the global Moran's I index of spatial autocorrelation. My second hypothesis is that the concentration of settlements having high or low crime values can be detected in the North-Hungarian Region. Considering settlement level data I made the following statements:

Thesis 5. It could be concluded that there is a regularity in spatial distribution of crime data by the help of global Moran's I spatial autocorrelation index: positive spatial autocorrelation was experienced in the relation of both crime indexes in significant part of the period under investigation. It refers that settlements having high crime rates can be found in the neighbourhood of high crime rate settlements; at the same time settlements having low crime rates are close to settlements having similar low crime values.

A. Besides that it can be concluded that the value of Moran's I index shows an increasing tendency concerning both crime indexes, which refers that the concentration of settlements having

low and high crime rates is getting more intensive.

Thesis 6. By the help of crime Hot Spot Analysis it was successful to delimit areas, where settlements with high or low crime rates concentrated. Determined hot and cold spots by Getis-Ord G_i^* local statistical method are justified by crime surface model as well.

A. Certain settlements situated in the southern part of Heves County have outstanding high crime rates (in the relation of both analysed period), the other problematic area is in the northern part of Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County (according to the maps of 2010/2011) (Figure 7 and 8). The definitely low population could influence the significance of the second group of hot spots.

B. In addition it is necessary to draw the attention for two areas according to the maps of 2010/2011, which appear as cold spots in the relation of both crime indexes. One of them is in the border of Nógrád and Pest County, while the other one is in the north-western and south-western neighbourhood of Miskolc.

Figure 7. Offence hot spot map of the North-Hungarian Region for 2010-2011 period
(Source: own edition)

During the studies I generated crime surface model, and I made the following statements:

Thesis 7. Crime surface models are the new generation of crime maps. By the help of surfacing processes crime becomes to be interpreted in three dimensions (Figure 9). The utilization of surface models would be

definitely justified in analysing larger spatial units – county, region, country –, because on the one hand they could help to support the explored nexus, on the other hand they could provide a better visualization method comparing to traditional thematic crime maps.

A. According to the opinion of JAKOBI (2009A) the same analytical capabilities are available for surface model generated from social data, like in case of traditional digital elevation models. It could be justified by a digital surface model generated by crime data.

Figure 8. Visualizing surface model in 3D generated from number of offences

(Source: own edition)

Several Hungarian literature dealt with the connection of crime and social factors, but the studying these relations with the help of mathematical-statistical methods were marginalized in criminology and sociology. I made the following findings:

Thesis 8. After overviewing the international articles focusing on the analysis of social background of crime it can be established, that they attempt to build a crime model by analysing only crimes against property; there are just a few which try to explain the whole criminality. In the aspect of methodologies it can be established that they use some kind of regression techniques.

Thesis 9. According to Pearson correlation coefficients the findings are the followings: there is a positive relationship between known offenders and proportion of jobseekers, the proportion of social assistance recipients, proportion of job-replacing assistance, unemployment rate and ethnic diversity. Negative relationship can be recognized in case of

following variables: comfort index, proportion of population having car, proportion of population aged punishable, education index, and numbers of elderly people for 100 children aged.

Thesis 10. I involved social factors having an effect on number of offenders into a regression model. As a result of that a crime model is built for the settlements of North-Hungarian Region, which supports fundamentally social disorganisation theory, and it explains the 23 % of variance of offenders for 100 000 residents. It is concluded that being unemployed and getting into the periphery of labour market can be defined as the highest risk factor in the aspect of crime offending.

A. Analysis of the four selected settlements are consistent with the results of crime model, with the only exception of religiousness. Mathematical relation between crime and religiousness could not be justified according to investigation performed in 453 settlements, but the beneficial effect of religiousness on public safety can be univocally established according to the experiences of the sample settlements.

CONCLUSION

There are several opportunities for utilizing the results of criminal geographical researches, including the adaptation of crime maps through operative police work. They could be utilized in the field of crime prevention, organisation of police patrol service, analytical-evaluation work, moreover in police leadership and education as well. In addition crime maps could be useful for making region development conceptions and urban planning (MÁTYÁS – SALLAI 2014).

It is worth to separate the opportunities provided by maps, which are drawn in different scales. Settlement-level crime maps could be utilized in the following fields: making spatial-specified crime prevention strategies, analytical and evaluation work, defining optimal place for police stations; defining optimal place for new penitentiary facilities considering the spatial distribution of offenders.

PÖDÖR (2007) lists the adaptation opportunities of crime maps in her conference presentation. Among them it is worth to underline the followings – in the level within the municipal level –: service management, organization of patrol routes; determining the area of law enforcement and criminal actions, organizing the quick close – for example in case of robbery –; locating missing person – delimiting the most optimal area for the sake of search; exploring crime series.

According to the opinion of MÁTYÁS – SALLAI (2014) crime maps are not appropriate by themselves for solving problems, but their utilization promote the police work. „Crime map is an opportunity for police experts, it cannot be ignored by the police of 21st Century through its everyday work” (MÁTYÁS – SALLAI 2014; 354P.).

REFERENCES

1. ACKERMAN, W. V. – MURRAY, A. T. (2004): Assessing spatial patterns of crime in Lima, Ohio. *Cities*. Vol. 21. No. 5. pp. 423-437.
2. ANDRESEN, M. A. (2011): Estimating the probability of local crime clusters: The impact of immediate spatial neighbors. *Journal of Criminal Justice*. 39. pp. 404.
3. APPIAHENE –GYAMFI, J. (2003): Urban crime trends and patterns in Ghana: The case of Accra. *Journal of Criminal Justice*. 31. pp. 13-23.
4. BREETZKE, D. G. (2010): Modeling violent crime rates: A test of social disorganization in the city of Tshwane, South Africa. *Journal of Criminal Justice*. 38. pp. 446-452.
5. BREETZKE, D. G. (2012): The effect of altitude and slope on the spatial patterning of burglary. *Applied Geography*. 34. pp. 66-75.
6. CAHILL, M. – MULLIGAN, G. (2007): Using Geographically Weighted Regression to Explore Local Crime Patterns. *Social Science Computer Review*. Vol. 25. No. 2. pp.174- 193.
7. CAMERON, J. G. (2001). *Spatial Analysis of Crime in Appalachia*. Washington, DC: National Institute of Justice, NCJ-189559.
8. CECCATO, V. – DOLMEN, L. (2011): Crime in rural Sweden. *Applied Geography*. 31. pp. 119-135.
9. CRACOLICI, M. F. – UBERTI, T. E. (2008): Geographical distribution of crime in Italian provinces: A spatial econometric analysis. *Nota di lavoro // Fondazione Eni Enrico Mattei: KTHC, Knowledge, technology, human capital*, No. 2008, 11. <http://www.feem.it/Feem/Pub/Publications/WPapers/default.htm> 2013. 07. 22.
10. ERDEI G. (2014): A bűnözésföldrajz elméleti és gyakorlati összefüggései. PhD értekezés. Nemzeti Közszolgálati Egyetem. Hadtudományi Doktori Iskola. 246p.
11. FAZEKAS G. (1997): Szarvas és vonzáskörzete a bűnözés tükrében (1986-1995). *Ügyészek Lapja*, 4. Évf. 3. Sz. Pp. 7-30.
12. FERGE ZS. (1999): Szegénység és bűnözés, azaz: van-e dezintegrációs és

decivilizációs veszély? Belügyi szemle, (47. Évf.) 2. Sz. pp. 3-27.

13. FERREIRA, J. – JOAO, P. – MARTINS, J. (2012): GIS for Crime Analysis: Geography for Predictive Methods. The Electronic Journal Information Systems Evaluation. Vol. 15. Issue 1. Pp. 36-49.
14. FÖLDES B. (1932): A bűnügyi statisztika problémái. Magyar Statisztikai Szemle, 3, 243-255. Idézve: Perényi R. (2006): A bűnözés mérése. Bűnügyi statisztika és bűnözéstörténet. (http://andorkaweb.tarki.hu/Konferenciak/Konferencia2006/Perenyi_Roland.pdf)
15. GÖNCZÖL K. (1993): A bűnözés társadalmi összefüggései. Társadalmi Szemle. 3. sz. pp. 37-48.
16. HARRIES, K. (2006): Extreme spatial variations in crime density in Baltimore County, MD. Geoforum. 37. Pp. 404-416
17. HELLER FARKAS T. (1964): A "bűnözési földrajz" elvi és módszertani problémái. Jogtudományi közlöny, 18. Évf. 8. Sz. pp. 451-460.
18. HORVÁTHNÉ TAKÁCS I. (2003): Bűnözési helyzetkép Baranya megyében a szocio- demográfiai adatok tükrében, 1990-2001. Területi statisztika, (6.(43.) Évf.) 5. Sz. pp.449- 475.
19. JAKOBI Á. (2009A): Felületmodellek és lejtők a társadalomföldrajzban, avagy térbeli interpoláció társadalomföldrajzi adatokon. Geoinformatika és domborzatmodellezés 2009. A HunDEM 2009 és a GeoInfo 2009 konferencia és kerekasztal válogatott tanulmányai. CD kiadvány.
20. KEREZSI K.- FINSZTER G. - KÓ J. - GOSZTONYI G.(2001): *A területi bűnmegelőzés lehetőségei Budapest V.,IX. és XXII. kerületében.* Kriminológiai Tanulmányok XXXVIII. kötet Országos Kriminológiai Intézet. Budapest, pp. 112-180.
21. KEREZSI K. – KÓ J. (2001): A IX. kerület bűnözési térképe. Belügyi Szemle. 7-8. pp. 100- 124.
22. KEREZSI K. – RITTER I. (2000): Budapest V. kerületének bűnözési térképe. Belügyi Szemle, 10. pp. 20-53.
23. KERTÉSZ I. (1999): A bűn európai útjain. Belügyi Szemle 9. pp. 45-100.
24. KOBOLKA I. – RITECZ GY. – SALLAI J. (2003): A Magyar Köztársaság államhatárának ezredfordulós kriminál földrajza. Szakmai Tudományos Közlemények, KBH Tudományos Kutatóhely és a MH Térképész Szolgálat, Budapest, pp. 82-97.
25. KOBOLKA I. – SALLAI J. (2008): Budapest kriminálgeográfiája 1960-1985 között. KBH Szakmai Szemle. 3. pp. 86-102.
26. KORINEK L. (1989a): A munkanélküliség és a bűnözés kapcsolatának néhány kérdése. Belügyi szemle, (27. Évf.) 8. Sz. pp.30-34.

27. KORINEK L. (1989b): A bűnözéstől való félelem és a tömegtájékoztatás, Belügyi szemle, (27. Évf.) 4. Sz. pp. 31-38.
28. KORINEK L.(1995): Félelem a bűnözéstől. Közgazdasági és Jogi Kiadó. 223p.
29. KOVACSICSNÉ NAGY K. (2010): A bűnözés területi sajátosságai (Három megye helyzetének összehasonlítása). Területi statisztika, 13. (50.). Évf. 3. Sz. Pp. 295-312
30. KOVÁCS Z. (1989): A bűnözésföldrajz lehetőségei hazánkban. Műhely 9. MTA FKI, Budapest, 11 p.
31. KÓ J. (2005): Félelem keletről nyugatra: A bűnözéstől való félelem területi sajátosságai Magyarországon. Kriminológiai tanulmányok. 42. köt. pp. 41-67.
32. LEI, L. (2011): The GIS-based Research on Criminal Cases Hotspots Identifying. Procedia Environmental Sciences. 12. pp. 957-963.
33. MÁTYÁS SZ. (2011): A Debreceni Rendőrkapitányság kriminálgeográfiai elemzése. Doktori (PhD) értekezés; Debreceni Egyetem, Természettudományi Doktori Tanács, Földtudományok Doktori Iskola, Debrecen 168p.
34. MÁTYÁS SZ. – SALLAI J. (2014): Kriminálgeográfia. In: Prof. Dr. Ruzsonyi P. (szerk.): Tendenciák és alapvetések a bűnügyi tudományok köréből. Nemzeti Közszolgálati és Tankönyv Kiadó. Budapest. pp. 335-356.
35. MESSNER, S. F. – ANSELIN, L. (2004): Spatial analyses of homicide with areal data. In: Goodchild, M. F. – Janelle D. G. (eds.): Spatially integrated social science. Oxford University Press, New York, NY, pp 127–144.
36. PATKÓS CS. – TÓTH A. (2012): A bűnözés néhány térbeli jellemzője a rendszerváltás után. Területi Statisztika. 3. pp. 250-263.
37. PISKÓTI ZS. (2010): A bűnözés területi eloszlása Magyarországon. In: Szűcs P. – Tompa R. (szerk.): Miskolci Egyetem Doktoranduszok Fóruma: Műszaki Földtudományi Kar Szekciókiadványa. Konferencia helye, ideje: Miskolc, Magyarország, 2010, Miskolc: Miskolci Egyetem Tudományszervezési és Nemzetközi Osztály, pp. 41-46.
38. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011A): A társadalomföldrajzi tényezők és a bűnözés összefüggéseinek vizsgálata Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén megyében. In: Dobróka M. – Gyulai Á. – Dabasi Halász Zs. (szerk.): Diáktudomány: A Miskolci Egyetem Tudományos Diákköri Munkáiból 2010-2011. Miskolc: Miskolci Egyetemi Kiadó, 2011. pp. 23-30.
39. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011B): A bűnözés és a társadalomföldrajzi tényezők kapcsolata négy Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén megyei település példáján. Ügyészek lapja 18:(2) pp. 5-10

40. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011C): Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén megye bűnözési helyzete. In: Bajmócy P. – Józsa K.(szerk.): Geográfus Doktoranduszok XI. Országos Konferenciája. Konferencia helye, ideje: Szeged, Magyarország, 2011.03.10-2011.03.11. Szeged: SZTE TTIK Gazdaság- és Társadalomföldrajz Tanszék, 2011. Paper 5.
41. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011D): Az Észak-magyarországi régió városainak bűnözési helyzete. Geotudományok: a Miskolci Egyetem közleménye: A sorozat, bányászat 82.: pp. 117- 121.
42. PISKÓTI ZS. (2012A): The statistical analysis of the position of the subjective safety in the tourism-frequented Miskolc-Tapolca. In: Strba, L. (editor): "Geotourism and its implications" International PhD. Conference. Kassa: TU Košice, 2012. pp. 99-102.
43. PISKÓTI ZS. – SISKÁNÉ SZILASI B. (2011): The human and criminal geographical characteristics of Bodroghöz. In: Kozma G. (szerk.): New Results of Cross-Border Co- Operation. Debrecen: Didakt Kiadó, 2011. pp. 77-85.
44. PISKÓTI-KOVÁCS ZS. – SISKÁNÉ SZILASI B. (2012): Criminal geographical analysis of three districts in Miskolc from the aspect of the tendencies of Hungary and the European Union. In: Berghauer S, et al. (eds.): Social geographical challenges in the Eastern Central Europe of the XXI. century: International geographical conference. pp. 375-382.
45. PÖDÖR A. (2007): Bűnügyi statisztikai adatok térképi ábrázolása. http://www.geo.info.hu/portal2007/images/stories/dokumentumok/20071113_Podor_A.pdf Utolsó letöltés: 2014. 09. 07.
46. RITECZ GY. – SALLAI J. (1999): Az államhatár 1998. évi kriminál földrajzi elemzése. Rendvédelmi füzetek 10. Rendőrtiszti Főiskola, Budapest, 27 p.
47. SALLAI J. (2002): Ukrán-magyar határ kriminál földrajza 1990-2002. In: Szónokyné Ancsin G. (szerk.): Határok és az Európai Unió. SZTE, Szeged, pp. 413-422.
48. SZABÓ A. – KOLTAINÉ TÓTH M. (1987): A bűnözés településhálózati megoszlása. Belügyi Szemle, 10. Idézte: Erdősi S. (2002): Régi-új javaslatok a bűnözés méréséhez. Belügyi Szemle, 2002. (50. Évf.) 4. Sz. pp. 109-128.
49. SZŰCS A. (2001): A fiatalkori bűnözés jellemzői Békés megyében. Statisztikai szemle, 79. évf. 4-5. sz. pp. 374-387.

50. TÓTH A. (2007): A bűnözés térbeli aspektusainak szociálgeográfiai vizsgálata Hajdú- Bihar megyében; Doktori (phd) értekezés; Debreceni Egyetem, Természettudományi Doktori Tanács, Földtudományok Doktori Iskola, Debrecen 250p.
51. VAVRÓ I. (1995): Társadalmi-demográfiai tényezők és a bűnözés. Állam és jogtudomány, (37. Évf.) 1-2. Sz. pp.170-176.
52. VÍGH J. - TAUBER I. - MADÁCSI I.(1989): A hátrányos társadalmi helyzet és a bűnözés kapcsolata. Belügyi szemle, (27. Évf.) 8. Sz. pp. 16-29.
53. VINCZE J. – FEKETE É. – KISGYÖRGY I. (1990): Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén megye környezetgazdálkodásának megalapozása. A társadalmi környezetszennyezés Borsod- Abaúj-Zemplén megyében. MTA RKK, Észak-magyarországi osztály, Miskolc, pp. 48- 73.
54. WANG, D. – DING, W. – LO, W. – MORABITO, M. – CHEN, P. – SALAZAR, J. – STEPINSKI, T. (2013): Understanding the spatial distribution of crime based on its related variables using geospatial discriminative patterns. Computers, Environment and Urban Systems. 39. pp. 93-106.

II. PUBLICATIONS BY THE AUTHOR RELATING TO DISSERTATION

1. PISKÓTI ZS. (2010): A társadalomföldrajzi tényezők és a bűnözés összefüggéseinek vizsgálata Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén megyében. In: Dobróka M. – Gyulai Á. – Dabasi Halász Zs. (szerk.): Diáktudomány. A Miskolci Egyetem Tudományos Diákköri Munkáiból 2009-2010. Miskolci Egyetemi Kiadó, Miskolc. pp. 23-30.
2. PISKÓTI ZS. (2010): A bűnözés területi megoszlása Magyarországon. In: Dr. Szűcs P., Tompa R.(szerk.): Miskolci Egyetem Doktoranduszok Fóruma: Műszaki Földtudományi Kar Szekciókiadványa. Doktoranduszok fóruma. pp.41-46.
3. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011): Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén megye bűnözési helyzete. In: Bajmócy P., Józsa K. (szerk.): Geográfus doktoranduszok XI. országos konferenciája. Szeged: SZTE TTIK Gazdaság- és Társadalomföldrajz Tanszék, 2011. Paper 5. (ISBN:978-963-306- 090-2)
4. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011): A bűnözés és a társadalomföldrajzi tényezők kapcsolata négy Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén megyei település példáján. Ügyészek lapja. XVIII. évf. 2. szám pp.5-10.

5. SISKÁNÉ DR. SZILASI B. – PISKÓTI ZS. (2011): The human and criminal geographical characteristics of Bodroghöz. In Kozma, G. (editor): New results of cross-border co- operation. ISBN: 978-963-89167-3-0. Didakt Kft., Debrecen. pp. 77-85.
6. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011): Az Észak-magyarországi régió városainak bűnözési helyzete. In Dobos E. – Siskáné Szilasi Beáta (szerk.): Geotudományok: A Miskolci Egyetem Közleménye: A sorozat, Bányászat 82. ISSN 1417-5398 pp. 117-121.
7. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011): Felületmodellezés alkalmazási lehetőségei bűnözésföldrajzi vizsgálatokban. In: Dr. Hegedűs András (szerk.): Lehetőségek a domborzatmodellezésben: A HunDEM 2011 konferencia és kerekasztal közleményei. Miskolc, Miskolci Egyetem Földrajz Intézete, 2012. pp. 1-7. (ISBN:978-863-358-006-6)
8. PISKÓTI ZS. (2011): Közép-Európa országainak bűnözési helyzete. In: Dr. Szűcs P., Tompa R. (szerk.): Doktoranduszok Fóruma Műszaki Földtudományi Kar Szekciókiadvány. Miskolci Egyetem Tudományszervezési és Nemzetközi Osztály. pp. 89-95.
9. PISKÓTI, ZS. (2012): The statistical analysis of the subjective safety feelings about public safety in the tourism-frequented Miskolc-Tapolca. In: Lubomir Strba (editor):"Geotourism and its implications" International PhD Conference. pp. 99-102. (ISBN: 978-80-553-0902-6)
10. PISKÓTI, ZS. (2012): Criminal geopgraphical analysis of three districts in Miskolc from the aspect of the tendencies of Hungary and the European Union. In: Berghauer S, et al.
11. Társadalomföldrajzi kihívások a XXI. század Kelet-Közép Európájában = Social geographical challenges in the Eastern Central Europe of the XXI. century: Nemzetközi földrajzi konferencia = international geographical conference. pp. 375-382. (ISBN:978-617-596-066-0)
12. SISKÁNÉ DR. SZILASI B. – PISKÓTI ZS. (2012): Miskolc idegenforgalmilag frekventált és elhanyagolt városrészeinek vizsgálata. In: Berghauer S, et al. (szerk.): Társadalomföldrajzi kihívások a XXI. század Kelet-Közép Európájában = Social geographical challenges in the Eastern Central Europe of the XXI. century: Nemzetközi földrajzi konferencia = international geographical conference. pp. 272-279.(ISBN: 978- 617-596-066-0)
13. PISKÓTI-KOVÁCS, ZS. (2013): Analysis of the residents' safety

feelings in the Avas- building estate (Miskolc) – Results of an empirical research. Forum geografic. Studii și cercetări de geografie și protecția mediului. (under publishing, accepted)

14. PISKÓTI-KOVÁCS ZS. (2013): Térinformatikai elemzési lehetőségek a bűnözésföldrajzi vizsgálatokban. Acta Academiae Paedagogicae Agriensis Sectio Geographiae (ISSN 1216-4208). (under publishing, accepted)
15. PISKÓTI-KOVÁCS ZS. – Siskáné Szilasi B. (2014): A bűnözés területi jellemzői Magyarországon a rendszerváltást követő időszakban. Ügyészek Lapja 24. évfolyam:(1.) pp. 57-66.
16. PISKÓTI-KOVÁCS ZS. (2014): Adalékok a bűnözés térinformatikai környezetben történő elemzéséhez. VII. Magyar Földrajzi Konferencia. Elektronikus Konferencia kiadvány, (under publishing) 9p.